

REFLECTIVE WRITING PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN THEIR ENGLISH FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSES AND STUDY SKILLS (EAPSS) MODULE

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Abstract:

English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) is a module that develops skills of students in terms of their listening, reading, reflective writing and in their oral presentation. It supports and motivates students in their skills in learning the module through strategies and academic achievement. The study aims to identify the reflective writing performance of students in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) module along the area of comprehension, key points, language proficiency, organization, and reliability. The study employs the quantitative descriptive approach as this design is judgmental. It provides a better analysis on the study under investigated. It elaborates the methods of research in the reflective writing and performance of the students. The respondents of the study are the students in Gulf College who are officially enrolled in English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS). They belong to Level 3 Block 2 for the academic year 2019-2020. The study comprised of Thirty (30) respondents only. Random Sampling is utilized in the study to assess the sample size of the study under investigated. It is focused on the variables of the comprehension level, key points, language proficiency, organization, and reliability on the assignment of students in their reflective writing journal under the English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills module and to achieve the desire sample size of the study (Gregoire, and Affleck, 2018). Result shows that performance level of students in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) in the area of comprehension is satisfactory which means level of performance is moderate, key points is satisfactory which means level of performance of students is moderate, language proficiency is satisfactory which means level of performance of students is moderate, organization is satisfactory which means level of performance of students is moderate, and reliability is poor which means level of performance of students is low.

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1. Introduction

English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) is a module that develops skills of students in terms of their listening, reading, reflective writing and in their oral presentation. It supports and motivates students in their skills in learning the module through strategies and academic achievement. Students registered in this module are trained to enhance their skills particularly in their reflective writing as part of their assessment in their assignment task (Wibrowski, Matthews, and Kitsantas, 2017).

Hence, the focus of this paper is to evaluate student performance in their reflective writing journal and the analysis of their comprehension level on the task given to them, key points on their reflective writing, language proficiency as needed on their module and skills as students, organization to the topic in writing and also the reliability of their writing that is free from plagiarism. Evaluating the performance of the students in their reflective writing will equip the module tutors to adjust their teaching strategies to better equip students in their learning knowledge and enhance their learning process in the module through developing curriculum in writing since the impact of the learning of the students fall on the module that demonstrates suitable knowledge and capability of the students (Squibb and Mikkelsen, 2016).

In addition, performance of the students is evaluated in the comprehension of the task given. They can write based on their choice topic. They are guided properly on the details of their writing, however; their comprehension level is measured on the text analysis and thorough details of their reflection. Comprehension is based on their analysis and discussion of the topic. It determines how effective students in their comprehension level as to writing their reflective journal through text. Improving their comprehension level may lead them to a better output of their reflective journal writing (Pyle, et. al., 2017). Details of the tasks are provided and students can manage through their comprehension since this is important in the task given to them. Discussion and concepts are taught in their reflective writing, however; they are given a choice to deal with their writing tasks. Students can better write when they analyse the task given because it is comprehension which lead them to a better writing skills. They are being influenced on the ideas being taught in their module tutors on the background of their writing and background of their topic. They need to understand the topic to provide outline as a guide for their writing. Comprehension on their writing must focus on language proficiency, forms, background, competency in the communication process and most especially on their critical thinking and comprehension of the tasks. It convinces students to develop their skills in writing as a part of their cognitive, growth and development (Foong, 2017).

Similarly, other performance to be evaluated among the students is the key points or details of their writing tasks. Key points are important to identify the key areas of their assignment. Ensures that all details of their tasks must be put in their assignment, objectives must be met and must be clearly stated. Key points must be reflected on their topic. They must have thorough knowledge on what they write as a part of the task given to them. Key points must be the basis of the discussion on their writing since this is an assignment for them to produce. There must be definite key points to identify for proper discussion which must be clearly written. Cues are highlights as key points of analysis in their reflective journal that is written systematically and is written step by step which is essential to the assessment of the students (Schneider, Lichtenberger, Mather, and Kaufman, 2018). Hence, students are responsible in identifying the key points of their topic that can explain details of the assignment. Knowledge is important to consider in this factor so that proper key points have a better picture in the assignment task. The challenge is on the part of the students on how to materialize their assignment tasks. Identifying the key points provide the reasoning power of the students in their writing as they are directed properly on the task given. It focuses on producing good work, output, and explores their communication practice. It can give details on the points to be accessed in their discourses (Eriksson, and Mäkitalo, 2015).

On the other hand, performance to be evaluated in their reflective journal writing is the language proficiency of the task. This deals on the mechanics of the task like grammar, vocabulary, correct usage, free from errors, structure, unity and clarity, and cohesiveness. Proper language must be reflected on the task. Write adequately on the task given. This measures the proficiency level of the students in their writing task assignment. Reflective writing provides ability on the analysis and critical thinking of the students. Students need to develop the skills of writing especially in the assignment. This ensures student to equip their knowledge and skills in their reflective writing as a best tool for the task given to them. Students perceive their skills in writing. The content is based on their proficiency in the language they used. Language proficiency contributes to the success of the students in their writing task (Sharif, and Zainuddin, 2017).

Nevertheless, organisation is one of the performances to be evaluated in the reflective writing journal of the students in their assignment task. Organization of the task requires accuracy on the assignment format, there must be a good impact in the different parts of the assignment like the introduction, body, and conclusion. It must be well-written and well-defined based on the format. The structure of the writing must be well-organised. The organization develops the concept and the theme of the task which is important to follow. It provides format for the reflective writing. It defines the topic to be written that will help students to write effectively. It facilitates proper organisation of the writing among the students. It analyses and outlines the topic to be written in a wise manner (Kahneman, and Henik, 2017). An organised topic provides clarity, objective and key points in the task. It clearly identifies the topic. There is a

continuous flow of the writing and explains details of the task effectively and efficiently. It provides a better picture of the task given or assignment.

Lastly, the performance of the reflective journal writing to be evaluated is the reliability of the task given. It is free from plagiarism. It is authentic and original because it passes through turnitin. It shows evidences and citation using the institutional requirement for references. Reliability is based on facts to prove what is written in the task required by the students. It is the tool to support what is written in the reflective writing task. The ability of the students to write a reliable source based on the topic and task provide a better skills for them to support the task through proper use of word, vocabulary, grammar, coherence, clarity and correct collaboration of the task. The best tool in writing the reflection of the students that shows reliability and validation on the task in the reflective writing journal (Moniz, Arntfield, Miller, Lingard, Watling, and Regehr, 2015).

2. Statement of the Problem

1. What is the level of performance of the students in their reflective writing on their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) along the area of
 - a. comprehension,
 - b. key points,
 - c. language proficiency,
 - d. organization, and
 - e. reliability?
2. Is there a significant correlation on the level of performance in their reflective writing in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) among them?

3. Research Design

The study employs the quantitative descriptive approach as this design is judgmental. It provides a better analysis on the study under investigated. It elaborates the methods of research in the reflective writing and performance of the students in the English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) in the area of comprehension, key points, language proficiency, organization, and reliability (Atmowardoyo, 2018).

3.1 Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study are the students in Gulf College who are officially enrolled in English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills. They belong to Level 3 Block 2 for the academic year 2019-2020. The study comprised of Thirty (30) respondents only.

3.2 Sampling Techniques

Random Sampling is utilized in the study. To assess the sample size of the study under investigated. It is focused on the variables under investigated particularly on the comprehension level, key points, language proficiency, organization, and reliability on the assignment of students in their reflective writing journal under the English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills module and to achieve the desire sample size of the study (Gregoire, and Affleck, 2018).

3.3 Research Instrument

1. Level of performance in terms of comprehension

4.20-5.00	Very Good	Comprehension level is above average
3.40-4.19	Good	Comprehension level is average
2.60-3.39	Satisfactory	Comprehension level is moderate
1.80-2.59	Poor	Comprehension level is low
1.00-1.79	Very Poor	Comprehension level is very low

2. Level of performance in terms of key points

4.20-5.00	Very Good	Key point level is above average
3.40-4.19	Good	Key point level is average
2.60-3.39	Satisfactory	Key point level is moderate
1.80-2.59	Poor	Key point level is low
1.00-1.79	Very Poor	Key point level is very low

3. Level of performance in terms of language proficiency

4.20-5.00	Very Good	Language proficiency level is above average
3.40-4.19	Good	Language proficiency level is average
2.60-3.39	Satisfactory	Language proficiency level is moderate
1.80-2.59	Poor	Language proficiency level is low
1.00-1.79	Very Poor	Language proficiency level is very low

4. Level of performance in terms of organisation

4.20-5.00	Very Good	Organisation level is above average
3.40-4.19	Good	Organisation level is average
2.60-3.39	Satisfactory	Organisation level is moderate
1.80-2.59	Poor	Organisation level is low
1.00-1.79	Very Poor	Organisation level is very low

5. Level of performance in terms of reliability

4.20-5.00	Very Good	Reliability level is above average
3.40-4.19	Good	Reliability level is average
2.60-3.39	Satisfactory	Reliability level is moderate
1.80-2.59	Poor	Reliability level is low
1.00-1.79	Very Poor	Reliability level is very low

4. Results

Table 1: Level of performance of the students in their reflective writing
in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS)

Indicators	VP	P	S	G	VG	WM	SD	Interpretation
Comprehension	2	3	13	3	4	2.63	0.043	Satisfactory
Key Points	1	1	14	4	5	2.87	0.053	Satisfactory
Language proficiency	1	1	17	4	2	2.67	0.045	Satisfactory
Organization	1	4	14	2	4	2.63	0.043	Satisfactory
Reliability	1	4	11	0	4	2.07	0.012	Poor
AWM	2	3	13	3	4	2.57		Poor

Legend: 4.20-5.00 - Very Good; 3.40-4.19 – Good; 2.60-3.39 – Satisfactory; 1.80-2.59 – Poor; 1.00-1.79 – Very Poor

Table 1 shows the level of performance of the students in their reflective writing assignment in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS). Comprehension is satisfactory (WM=2.63) which means the level of performance of students is moderate, key points is satisfactory ((WM=2.87) which means the level of performance of students is moderate, language proficiency is satisfactory (WM=2.67) which means the level of performance of students is moderate, organization is satisfactory (WM=2.63) which means the level of performance of students is moderate, and reliability is poor (WM=2.07) which means the level performance of students is low and the overall (AWM=2.57) is poor which means the level performance of the students is low.

Table 2 shows the significant correlation on the level of performance in their reflective writing in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS). When different variables are tested against each other it shows that the result is not significant because the critical r-value is lower than the computed r-value of 0.361. This shows that there is no significant relationship on the level of performance of the students in their reflective writing assignment. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 2: Results of the significant correlation on the level of performance in their reflective writing in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS)

Variable	Computed r-value	Relationships *significant * not significant	Hypotheses *accepted *rejected
Comprehension			
1. key points	0.089	not significant	accepted
2. language proficiency	0.092	not significant	accepted
3. organisation	0.092	not significant	accepted
4. reliability	0.104	not significant	accepted
Key Points			
1. comprehension	0.089	not significant	accepted
2. language proficiency	0.088	not significant	accepted
3. organisation	0.089	not significant	accepted
4. reliability	0.100	not significant	accepted
Language Proficiency			
1. comprehension	0.092	not significant	accepted
2. key points	0.088	not significant	accepted
3. organisation	0.092	not significant	accepted
4. reliability	0.103	not significant	accepted
Organisation			
1. comprehension	0.092	not significant	accepted
2. key points	0.089	not significant	accepted
3. language proficiency	0.092	not significant	accepted
4. reliability	0.104	not significant	accepted
Reliability			
1. comprehension	0.104	not significant	accepted
2. key points	0.100	not significant	accepted
3. language proficiency	0.103	not significant	accepted
4. reliability	0.104	not significant	accepted

Significant at 0.05 level, one-tailed test, df at 28 with critical r-value of 0.361

5. Discussion

Students are given task to do as part of the assessment in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS). Details of the assignment are explained for the students to follow. Frameworks are given emphasis as a guide in making their assignment. They are being evaluated on the performance in terms of comprehension, key points, language proficiency, organisation, and reliability. Assessment is given to identify the performance of students in their skills in English. Enhancing their language proficiency better equip student in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) giving emphasis on the module requirements, adopting English as their foreign language, and to develop students in their learning engagement in the module, assessing the performance in their module output (Fenton-Smith, Humphreys, Walkinshaw, Michael, and Lobo, 2017).

In the area of comprehension, the level of performance of the student is satisfactory which means students in this level are moderate. The students understand

what they write but need to focus more on the mechanics of the assignment as to word usage, grammar, coherence and unity to provide a better output in the task. They know what to write however, the problem is they are running out of words, they can say something behind at their back but they cannot write exactly the tasks according to the structure of the assignment. Students can write their assignment based on their comprehension level, however; they have difficulties on the construction of their English because English for them is a foreign language. Moreover, they have limited knowledge on the language where they need to improve the language to achieve comprehension on the task given. Consider the ability of the students who have a weak foundation in the language because they are just beginners to study English. They can broaden or widen their knowledge to English to have a better comprehension of the English language and write effective assignment. Crafting an assignment with better comprehension on the task will enhance students in their craft of writing. Students must have a target clear on what to write since the task is an assignment. They need to formulate an assignment task beyond their comprehension level, try to search for the topic assign to them. Make an action plan or outline on the task given. Most of all, students must understand full the task for better comprehension and thus; helping them to be effective in the task they want to achieve (Brookhart, 2017).

On the other hand, results of key points among the respondents show satisfactory which means performance level of students is moderate. They have something to say and something to write by identifying key points that serves as guide in the writing of the task however, they have difficulties in identifying because most of the words are unfamiliar that lead them to confusion. The translation they have in the google is not reliable sometimes because some words have no translation in Arabic and in English vice versa. Key points demonstrate how students do their task particularly on the information needed in the assignment for the proper key words as outline in the task given (Fink, 2019). Acknowledge the sources of the key points on the proficiency in writing must be the goal of students in the module to have an effective assignment because it is a challenge among the students to write. Identification of key points is a challenge among the students to explore because it is a skill in writing in the English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS). It focuses on the text to write as guide or outline in the task of the assignment. This is the skills that students need to develop because they are trained to write in all their assignments in content and in an instructional assignment needed in their learning skills (Wette, 2017).

Furthermore, results of the language proficiency on the level performance of the students show satisfactory which means moderate. Students in this area have background and knowledge on English, however; they need to improve and give emphasis on grammar and structure of the language. They can express themselves in writing however, the structure of the sentences, and words usage is a problem. Particularly on the punctuation marks, spelling and proper capitalization on the words in which situation affects the assignment of the students in content and in thoughts (MacIntyre, 2017). Many issues on the language proficiency of the students where

module tutors need to address. Though different theories are taught particularly on the correct usage of the language, however; the effectiveness of the students in their proficiency must be to practice and practice the theory so that they will use to it. Constant practice will make language proficiency merit their learning process. The effectiveness of their learning process generates knowledge in English that make them proficient in the language. Remember that English for them is foreign not their second language, they have difficulty in adapting to new learning in the language. They need to be more proficient so that their writing performance will not be affected because from time to time all their modules require writing of their assignment as part of their assessment. Module tutors should encourage their students to be vigilant in their language learning for them to be effective and efficient in their learning improvement (Stapa, and Majid, 2017).

Whereas, result of the organisation in the assignment task of the students show satisfactory which means level of performance of the students is moderate. This is one of the problems of the students is the organisation of the text in their assignment task. Though proper format are given emphasis by the module tutors, students have difficulties in writing the introduction, body, and conclusion of the task assignment. They must need to give emphasis on the organisation of the task since they are being marked according to the criteria given. Organisation will give a better impact on the task given. It will entice the examiner to read their assignment in accordance to the topic given. Once the assignment is written properly with correct organisation, the output of the assignment is efficient and effective and the result is better. In addition, it helps the students to write effectively and enhance their knowledge in their module. It will help to develop more skills in writing. Organisation in writing needs to plan for the sequence of the assignment which is important factor to consider and for the students to develop since this is also a skill among them. Consider the topic that needs to be emphasised in the organisation of the assignment. Organisation helps in the analysis of the tasks that need to be addressed for the writing task. Organisation of the writing task is a challenge among the students because it explains the task thoroughly to have an efficient output in the assignment. Analysing critically the writing task organisation will lead to a better writing development of the students. This can be applied in all the assignment in their modules in the college (Philippakos, 2018). Similarly, it expresses to expand, to analyse, and to think the proper organization of the assignment task of the respondents. Depicting proper organization will help the students lessen their burden in the writing of their assignment task (Thornton III, Mueller-Hanson, and Rupp, 2017). Indeed, the results show poor in the area of reliability on the level of performance of the students which means low. It shows that students have difficulties in the sources of their assignment though sources are taught to them since it is important as part of the requirements in the assignment task. Techniques in finding resources must be given emphasis because it is important as added knowledge when students write an assignment task, particularly in the text citation and referencing as part of the institutional requirement for the task. Reliability has an annotation on the assignment

task of the students. It labels the source of information of the assignment. Finding a better reliability provide the tool for analysing the writing of their assignment (Crible, and Degand, 2019).

6. Conclusions

Performance level of students in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills in the area of comprehension shows satisfactory which means level of performance is moderate, key points is satisfactory which means level of performance of students is moderate, language proficiency is satisfactory which means level of performance of students is moderate, organization is satisfactory which means level of performance of students is moderate, and reliability is poor which means level of performance of students is low.

7. Recommendations

Students need to focus on the skills in comprehension, key points, language proficiency and organization because the result is moderate. They need to improve in these skills because it is important in their assignment task by learning more techniques to improve their reflective writing tasks. Practice and practice on the task given because it is a part of their learning process and enhancement. Intensive review on the criteria of the writing task to obtain better marks and understanding on the task given, on the other hand; they need to improve in sourcing reliability on the assignment task which is important in their reflective journal. Proper text citation and proper referencing must be followed thoroughly.

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